

CURRENT STATE OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF GLIAL BRAIN TUMORS

¹Kadyrbekov R.T., ²Sizdikhodjayev S.A., ³Altybayev U.U., ⁴Zekriyayev N.N., ⁵Gabbazov A.K.

^{1,2,3,4,5}Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Neurosurgery

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Abstract. Gliomas are one of the most common primary tumors of the central nervous system, and surgery remains the mainstay of treatment for gliomas of any grade. In this study, based on the introduction of gliomas, we review new surgical techniques and technologies to support the extent of resection to achieve long-term disease control and summarize the findings on how to maintain a balance between cytoreduction and neurological morbidity from the literature review. With modern neurosurgical techniques, glioma resection can be performed safely with a low rate of postoperative complications and excellent long-term functional outcomes.

Keywords: review, intraoperative techniques, extent of resection, gliomas, imaging technologies, intraoperative stimulation mapping, awake craniotomy, high-definition tractography and fluorescein.

Introduction

Gliomas originate from glial cells of the central nervous system (CNS) and are the most common primary CNS tumors. According to the 2021 World Health Organization (WHO) classification of CNS tumors, gliomas are classified as low-grade gliomas (LGG; WHO grade II or I) and high-grade gliomas (HGG; WHO grade III or IV). Supratentorial gliomas account for approximately 30% of all primary intracranial tumors in adults, and more than 50% of them are high-grade gliomas (HGG) (1). Tumor grade is influenced by several clinical factors (both pathological and non-pathological), including pathological features such as nuclear atypia, mitotic activity, vascular proliferation, necrosis, etc., as well as non-pathological features such as the clinical course and treatment outcome (2). Glioma is more common in whites and blacks, with a 1.5-fold higher incidence in men than in women (3). China is one of the countries with the highest prevalence and mortality rate of CNS tumors (4). The overall age-adjusted incidence rates for all gliomas range from 4.67 to 5.73 per 100,000 people (5, 6). The median overall survival (OS) times are 78.1, 37.6, and 14.4 months for low-grade gliomas, anaplastic gliomas, and glioblastomas, respectively (7). Most glioma cases are sporadic in origin, although some are associated with Mendelian disorders such as tuberous sclerosis, neurofibromatosis type 1 or type 2, and so on (8). There are several factors that influence the prognosis, including the Karnofsky score at diagnosis, histology, and molecular markers. Age and tumor histology have been identified as major predictors of patient prognosis (9, 10). Previous brain or scalp irradiation may increase the risk of developing gliomas (11, 12).

Gliomas exhibit different symptoms depending on the tumor size and location. A systematic review summarizes the frequency of symptoms and highlights several symptoms, among which the most common are seizures, cognitive deficits, somnolence, and dysphagia at different stages (13). In these tumors, seizures are the most common symptom because they are highly epileptogenic. This is true for both low-grade and high-grade gliomas. The risk of seizures varies from 60% to 100% in low-grade gliomas and from 40% to 60% in glioblastomas (14).

Seizure control and reduction of neurocognitive deficits are the main treatment goals for some patients diagnosed with glioma, which they always strive for.

The principle of surgical treatment of gliomas is to reduce the volumetric impact caused by tumors, maximize the extent of resection, and minimize damage to surrounding tissues, especially in the case of gliomas located in functionally significant areas, in order to preserve neurological function. Treatment procedures vary depending on the grade of gliomas. We will consider low-grade gliomas, high-grade gliomas, and recurrent gliomas separately.

Low grade gliomas

Low-grade gliomas account for up to 15% of all adult brain tumors (15). Several volumetric studies support the idea of the importance of the extent of resection (EOR) in improving the survival of patients with low-grade gliomas. These studies have shown that the median survival time ranges from 61.1 to 90.5 months with maximal resection (10, 16, 17). Low-grade gliomas are the most common and ultimately fatal disease among young adults (median age 41 years), with a median survival of approximately 7 years (18). EOR is a statistically significant predictor of overall survival. These studies highlight the importance of achieving complete resection. Low-grade gliomas have a diverse anatomical, histopathological, and molecular profile that reflects clinical outcome (19). In addition to influencing the overall survival of patients with low-grade gliomas, EOR also affects the malignancy rate and seizure-free status (20). A retrospective study including 153 patients with gliomas who were divided into watch-and-wait and early surgical resection groups, respectively, showed that patients with low-grade gliomas who underwent early surgery had a higher chance of survival, suggesting that the timeliness of resection is critical (21).

High grade gliomas

For patients with primary high-grade gliomas (HGG) such as glioblastoma, a retrospective analysis of a randomized trial showed that survival and disease-free survival are highly dependent on the extent of tumor resection; the fact that incomplete resections result in more rapid neurological deterioration also supports the importance of complete resection for disease-free survival (22–24).

One retrospective study comparing “total” and “subtotal” resection data showed that total resection of HGG provided a higher survival rate at 1 year of follow-up, which decreased to 19% at 2 years, compared with subtotal resection (25). Some MRI scans in patients diagnosed with HGG always show a non-enhancing abnormal area, so studying the effect of resection level on this area remains unclear. Li reported that the group undergoing total resection of $\geq 53.21\%$ of the surrounding FLAIR abnormality beyond 100% of contrast-enhancing resection had a significant increase in survival compared with less extensive resection ($p < 0.001$) (26).

In a discussion of the extent and rate of resection, Sanai reported that for glioblastoma multiforme (GBM) tumors, aggressive resection (EOR) is associated with improved overall survival, even at the highest resection levels. A significant survival benefit was observed with resection volumes as low as 78%, and stepwise survival improvement was evident even in the range of 95%–100% resection volume (27).

Recurrent gliomas

Regardless of the classification of recurrent gliomas (LGG or HGG), many patients accept repeat resection as a routine treatment option to maintain a good quality of life (28). A significant benefit was noted in 52 patients with reoperated low-grade gliomas; the principle of repeat surgery showed an overall 10-year survival rate of 57%; various prognostic factors, such as the use of

early-stage radiotherapy and pathology at recurrence, influenced overall survival (29). A large study of recurrent high-grade gliomas showed a median overall survival of 19 months and a median recurrence-free survival of 5.2 months after repeat resection, suggesting that the survival benefit of microsurgical resection was not diminished despite biological progression (30). Currently, the clinical benefits of reoperation for both recurrent low-grade and high-grade gliomas demonstrate that the extent of resection may be the strongest predictor of overall survival in each individual patient.

Improvements in surgical techniques and neurosurgical instruments facilitate the practice of neuro-oncology, while improving treatment outcomes and maximizing cytoreduction in patients with gliomas. Modern neurosurgical imaging techniques, including intraoperative neuronavigation (31, 32), tractography DTI (33), intraoperative MRI (IoMRI) (34, 35), intraoperative ultrasound (IoUS) (36, 37), fluorescence-guided surgery (38, 39), intraoperative stimulation mapping (IoSM), awake craniotomy (AC) approach (40, 41), high-fidelity augmented reality tractographic imaging, and fluorescein (AR HDFT - F) (42, 43), intraoperative portable microscopy and intraoperative mutational analysis have improved the rate of complete radiographic resection of gliomas.

Neuronavigation systems

Neuronavigation systems are widely used in glioma surgery and provide many benefits to surgeons. Among the main advantages are accurate preoperative planning of craniotomy in real time and identification of small intracranial lesions. In addition to the basic settings, it is now also possible to add functional MRI (fMRI) and tractography information DTI as overlays available to the surgeon during surgery. MRI does not use radiation; it can produce images with high spatial resolution down to the millimeter, but with low temporal resolution due to a 5-second delay between initial neural activity and the image; it can only capture a clear picture of brain activity when the patient is still, but not instantaneous brain activity. Neuronavigation can create connections between volumetric lesions and functional areas. A randomized controlled trial investigating the effectiveness of neuronavigation found that the mean amount of residual tumor tissue was 13.8% in neuronavigated surgeries compared with 28.9% in standard surgeries, although there was no evidence to support the use of neuronavigation to improve the extent of tumor resection based on lesion size or location (33).

Tractography

Diffusion tensor imaging (DTI) based tractography is used to plan major fibrotic tracts in 3D and avoid damaging important white matter in the brain. Visualized white matter groups are integrated into the 3D model to minimize the level of surgical morbidity caused by disruption of important white matter bundles.

However, some perioperative studies investigating the effect of DTI neuronavigation on reducing morbidity have not shown clear evidence due to tumor infiltration and edema (31, 44, 45). Given the lack of accuracy in defining functional areas, DTI cannot be used as an independent tool for surgical decision making. Currently, diffusion-weighted MRI as a new technique is used to overcome the previous problem of accurately mapping peritumoral edematous tissue (46).

Intraoperative MRI

Intraoperative MRI (IoMRI) is changing the approach to glioma treatment. IoMRI not only helps to address the issue of brain displacement, but also helps the neurosurgeon to identify tumor remnants and achieve a higher extent of resection (EOR). In a prospective study including 100 adult patients undergoing glioma surgery using IoMRI and neuronavigation, Leroy reported a

median resection volume of 100%, regardless of glioma type and location. The only exception was the insula, where remnant levels were higher. There was no difference in the median Karnofsky performance status (KPS) between low-grade gliomas (LGGs) and high-grade gliomas (HGGs) at different stages of postoperative follow-up. He also introduced the concept of “staged volumetric” surgery to ensure high safety for the surgeon and low morbidity for patients (47). Several other unregulated studies also suggest that IoMRI may improve resection rates of both low- and high-grade gliomas, preserve neurological function, and prolong patient survival (48–50).

Intraoperative ultrasound

Intraoperative ultrasound (IoUS) is an affordable tool that can be easily integrated into existing infrastructure and operative workflows. IoUS has evolved significantly with well-integrated navigation tools and improved image quality compared to previous artifact-prone image quality (51). However, IoUS is challenging to use in detecting tumor remnants smaller than 1 cm in diameter (52), and the cone-shaped field of view can sometimes make lesion visualization difficult.

Fluorescence-guided surgery

Recently, intraoperative fluorescence-guided surgery using 5-aminolevulinic acid (5-ALA) has been widely used (22, 53). 5-ALA, being a prodrug for heme, can be converted to protoporphyrin IX (PpIX), which accumulates predominantly in tumor cells and epithelial tissues when administered across an intact blood-brain barrier (BBB) (53, 54). The red-violet fluorescence properties of PpIX are used to detect tumor tissues during glioma resection (38, 39).

The sensitivity of 5-ALA for gliomas has been demonstrated to be up to 95% in one study, supporting its utility as an emerging technology (55). The specificity of 5-ALA in predicting malignant tissue varies widely, with most studies reporting >70% (56–58). Visible fluorescence varies with glioma grade, with 95.4% in glioblastomas versus 24.1%–26.3% in grade I and II gliomas (59). Alessandro reported results of 5-ALA fluorescence-guided resection: overall complete resection of >98% was achieved in 93% of patients with HGG, with fluorescent tissue margins exceeding neuronavigation-defined tumor margins in 43% of patients (60).

Intraoperative 5-ALA fluorescence is ineffective in targeting low-grade gliomas (LGG) because they do not produce a level of fluorescence visible to the naked eye (38). Therefore, intraoperative confocal microscopy techniques for 5-ALA-based tumor fluorescence imaging have been developed and used during LGG resection procedures. Using this microscopy, PpIX fluorescence has been detected in cellular infiltration identified at the margins of WHO grade I and II tumors (61).

Mapping functional cortex areas and awake surgery

Because intraoperative stimulation mapping (IS) allows for more precise definition of functional areas (especially in the dominant hemisphere), it has become the standard of choice for treating tumors in significant brain areas. This allows surgeons to achieve a greater extent of resection (EOR) and reduce postoperative morbidity.

This technique involves electrical stimulation to depolarize a specific area of the functional cortex. The electrode precisely stimulates focal neurons, depolarizes them, transmits a signal to the area of interest, and causes local excitation, inhibition, or possibly propagation of the signal to distant sites (40). The entire process can be monitored by an electrophysiologist if the patient is performing motor or language tasks. Using a bipolar probe, the neurosurgeon can perform more precise mapping.

Sometimes the glioma lesion is located within functional cortical areas of the brain. Neurosurgeons cannot use classical central nervous system (CNS) anatomy to predict functional areas (such as speech or motor areas) due to individual cortical heterogeneity (62, 63). Tumor effects can distort brain topography, and brain plasticity can cause reorganization of functional networks (64).

A meta-analysis including patients with supratentorial gliomas showed that total resections were achieved in 75% of patients resected using IoSM compared to 58% of patients without intraoperative mapping; however, IoSM did not affect the extent of resection (65). Another meta-analysis showed similar results, especially regarding delayed severe deficits, demonstrating a significant reduction in their incidence (3.4%) in patients using IoSM (63), and these deficits were always transient due to brain structures adjacent to the resection cavity. The use of IoSM during resection surgery reduces the incidence of late severe neurological deficits (65).

Awake craniotomy (AC) is recommended for surgical treatment of gliomas involving dominant mid-posterior frontal, temporal, and mid-anterior parietal lobes. AC techniques allow more effective monitoring of complex cognitive functions such as spatial and emotional recognition (41).

According to some data, the maximum duration of time that patients can remain awake and perform mapping tasks is about 1 hour. During this period, various series of IoSM tasks are performed, such as language tasks (primary tasks are number counting and picture naming) and non-language tasks (vision and other higher cognitive functions, including calculation, working memory, and music) (66, 67). When tumors are located near speech or motor networks, the use of direct cortical stimulation is recommended to preserve function in appropriate patients. This often requires awake craniotomy, for which technical and anesthetic considerations have been previously described (68). If gliomas are located in an area associated with severe complications, the rate of permanent complications using AC techniques will be about 10% (69).

A random effects meta-analysis showed that AC (90.1%) provided a larger mean resection volume than general anesthesia (GA) (81.7%), which was confirmed ($p = 0.06$). For the analysis, neurological deficits were stratified by severity and time of occurrence. Early and late neurological deficits, as well as minor and major complications, were not significantly different between patients undergoing AC and GA, respectively. The results showed that IoSM in resection of gliomas located in significant areas can be performed safely and effectively using AC (70).

Other mapping methods

There are other adjunctive methods of intraoperative stimulation mapping (IoSM). Functional MRI (fMRI) generally provides important information about the location of sensory and motor pathways, but it is not able to map language areas (71). Phase reversal somatosensory evoked potential (SSEP) techniques can be used to localize the primary sensory cortex. However, the SSEP level is only useful for localizing the primary somatosensory cortex (72).

High-precision tractography and fluorescein

Similar to 3D virtual object modeling with real objects, the application of augmented reality (AR) in neurosurgery has the potential to change the way neurosurgeons plan and perform surgical procedures. Augmented reality neuronavigation system has been used in surgical planning (73) by integrating MRI or CT images into the surgical field (74). In a review by Lopez et al., AR was shown to be the second most commonly used tool in brain tumors, allowing the neurosurgeon to localize tract fibers and guide resection (42). It may improve intraoperative safety by facilitating

and simplifying selective anatomy of the lesion and adjacent structures, although there is currently no established method to accurately measure 3D errors and displacements in deep lesions.

High-fidelity fiber tractography using DTI (HDFT) has been validated as a useful tool for planning glioma resection and assessing postoperative fiber tract connectivity (43). Sodium fluorescein (F) has been used as a fluorescent dye in high-grade gliomas (HGG) to increase the extent of resection (75). Although there are many limitations, several studies have addressed the combined use of AR and HDFT - F. AR HDFT - F improves the intraoperative spatial positioning of the neurosurgeon and allows differential visualization of each tract as needed. Luzzi included 117 patients with newly diagnosed supratentorial HGG, of which 54 were operated using the AR technique HDFT - F, and 63 - using traditional neuronavigation. The results showed that the AR group HDFT - F had a greater resection volume and longer recurrence-free survival, although there was no difference in complication rates between the two groups. AR- assisted surgery HDFT - F is considered a safe and effective procedure for restoring neurological function in patients. However, current procedures only involve patients under general anesthesia, and the entire process is still limited by the fact that DTI only provides anatomical information (76).

Other intraoperative instruments

There are other intraoperative tools designed to achieve maximal tumor resection, and most of them are still under discussion.

1. Intraoperative portable microscopy

A single optical fiber is combined with miniature scanning and optical systems to provide high-resolution images (77) in this technique. This technique allows problems to be addressed at the cellular level. Histologic characteristics of gliomas, meningiomas, and central neurocytomas have been distinguished using intraoperative confocal microscopy for fluorescein imaging (78). Further studies are needed to determine whether this technique can be used to complement resection procedures and traditional neuropathologic diagnostic techniques.

2. Intraoperative mutation analysis

Mutation analysis can be used in real time to theoretically define true tumor boundaries. These methods include genotyping of known tumor mutations using PCR-based approaches such as isocitrate dehydrogenase 1 or 2 (IDH 1/2) aberrations (79); mass spectrometry based on defined tumor spectral profiles, which is similar to magnetic resonance spectroscopy methods (80). All of these methods require further testing for specificity and sensitivity in glioma resection

Table 1. Treatment options.

Stages	Technique and methodology	Advantages
Preoperative	Neuronavigation systems	Accurate preoperative craniotomy planning in real time and identification of small intracranial lesions. Ability to add functional MRI and tractography information intraoperatively.
Preoperative	Tractography	Plan major fibrous tracts in 3D and avoid damaging important white matter bundles.

Intraoperative	Intraoperative MRI (IoMRI)	Addressing the issue of brain displacement and increasing the extent of resection (EOR).
Intraoperative	Intraoperative ultrasound (IOUS)	A tool that can be easily integrated into the operational process to detect residues larger than 1 cm in diameter.
Intraoperative	Fluorescence- guided surgery	Red-violet light fluorescence: for detection of tumor tissues during resection of HGGs. Intraoperative fluorescence confocal microscopy: for LGGs.
Intraoperative	Intraoperative stimulation mapping (IoSM) and awake craniotomy (AC) approach	Resection of gliomas located in significant areas can be performed safely and effectively.
Intraoperative	High-precision fiber tractography with augmented reality and fluorescein (AR HDFT - F)	Improved intraoperative spatial positioning and differential visualization of each tract.
Intraoperative	Intraoperative portable microscopy	Solving problems at the cellular level with a single optical fiber.
Intraoperative	Intraoperative mutational analysis	Genotyping and real-time mass spectrometry to determine true tumor boundaries.

Conclusions

Preoperative (such as neuronavigation systems and tractography DTI) and intraoperative (including IoMRI, IoUS, fluorescence-guided surgery, IoSM and AC, AR approaches HDFT - F, intraoperative portable microscopy and mutation analysis) surgical methods of glioma therapy provide neurosurgeons with many opportunities to increase the volume of resection of gliomas of any degree (Table 1). The neuronavigation system is always used for accurate preoperative planning. Tractography DTI allows surgical path planning while avoiding significant white matter bundles. IoMRI can address the problem of intraoperative brain displacement.

IoUS can be easily integrated into surgery to detect remnants larger than 1 cm in diameter. Fluorescence-guided surgery can detect tumors in the HGG and LGG using confocal microscopy and fluorescence. IoSM and AC approaches can be used for gliomas located in functionally significant areas.

AR HDFT - F can improve intraoperative spatial positioning and allow differential visualization of each tract. Intraoperative portable microscopy and mutation analysis, although further testing is needed, also provide methods for glioma resection.

The development of surgical techniques has changed the principles of glioma treatment, making them more accurate, effective and real-time, which can maximize the tumor resection volume, preserve neurological functions near the affected area, reduce morbidity and improve treatment outcomes.

REFERENCES

1. Luzzi S, Giotta Lucifero A, Martinelli A, Maestro MD, Savioli G, Simoncelli A, et al. Supratentorial high-grade gliomas: Maximal safe anatomical resection guided by augmented reality high-definition fiber tractography and fluorescein. *Neurosurg Focus* (2021) 51(2): E5. doi: [10.3171/2021.5.FOCUS21185](https://doi.org/10.3171/2021.5.FOCUS21185)
2. Louis DN, Ohgaki H, Wiestler OD, Cavenee WK, Burger PC, Jouvet A, et al. The 2007 WHO classification of tumors of the central nervous system. *Acta Neuropathol (Berl)* (2007) 114:97–109. doi: [10.1007/s00401-007-0243-4](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00401-007-0243-4)
3. Ostrom QT, Gittleman H, Stetson L, Virk SM, Barnholtz-Sloan JS. Epidemiology of gliomas. *Cancer Treat Res* (2015) 163:1–14. doi: [10.1007/978-3-319-12048-5_1](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-12048-5_1)
4. Chen W, Zheng R, Baade PD, Zhang S, Zeng H, Bray F, et al. Cancer statistics in China, 2015. *CA Cancer J Clin* (2016) 66:115–32. doi: [10.3322/caac.21338](https://doi.org/10.3322/caac.21338)
5. Larjavaara S, Mantyla R, Salminen T, Haapasalo H, Raitanen J, Jääskeläinen J, et al. Incidence of gliomas by anatomic location. *Neuro Oncol* (2007) 9(3):319–25. doi: [10.1215/15228517-2007-016](https://doi.org/10.1215/15228517-2007-016)
6. Gousias K, Markou M, Voulgaris S, Goussia A, Voulgari P, Bai M, et al. Descriptive epidemiology of cerebral gliomas in northwest Greece and study of potential predisposing factors, 2005-2007. *Neuroepidemiology* (2009) 33(2):89–95. doi: [10.1159/000222090](https://doi.org/10.1159/000222090)
7. Yang P, Wang Y, Peng X, You G, Zhang W, Yan W, et al. Management and survival rates in patients with glioma in China (2004-2010): A retrospective study from a single-institution. *J Neuro-Oncol* (2013) 113(2):259–66. doi: [10.1007/s11060-013-1103-9](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11060-013-1103-9)
8. Ostrom QT, Bauchet L, Davis FG, Deltour I, Fisher JL, Langer CE, et al. The epidemiology of glioma in adults: A “state of the science” review. *Neuro-oncol* (2014) 16:896–913. doi: [10.1093/neuonc/nou087](https://doi.org/10.1093/neuonc/nou087)
9. Sanai N, Chang S, Berger MS. Low-grade gliomas in adults. *J Neurosurg* (2011) 115:948–65. doi: [10.3171/2011.7.JNS101238](https://doi.org/10.3171/2011.7.JNS101238)
10. Sanai N, Berger MS. Glioma extent of resection and its impact on patient outcome. *Neurosurgery* (2008) 62:753–64. doi: [10.1227/01.neu.0000318159.21731.cf](https://doi.org/10.1227/01.neu.0000318159.21731.cf)
11. Preston DL, Ron E, Yonehara S, Kobuke T, Fujii H, Kishikawa M, et al. Tumors of the nervous system and pituitary gland associated with atomic bomb radiation exposure. *J Natl Cancer Inst* (2002) 94:1555–63. doi: [10.1093/jnci/94.20.1555](https://doi.org/10.1093/jnci/94.20.1555)
12. Sadetzki S, Chetrit A, Freedman L, Stovall M, Modan B, Novikov I. Long-term follow-up for brain tumor development after childhood exposure to ionizing radiation for tinea capitis. *Radiat Res* (2005) 163:424–32. doi: [10.1667/RR3329](https://doi.org/10.1667/RR3329)
13. IJzerman-Korevaar M, Snijders TJ, de Graeff A, Teunissen SCCM, de Vos FYF. Prevalence of symptoms in glioma patients throughout the disease trajectory: A systematic review. *J Neurooncol* (2018) 140(3):485–96. doi: [10.1007/s11060-018-03015-9](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11060-018-03015-9)
14. Vecht CJ, Kerkhof M, Duran-Pena A. Seizure prognosis in brain tumors: new insights and evidence-based management. *Oncologist* (2014) 19(7):751–9. doi: [10.1634/theoncologist.2014-0060](https://doi.org/10.1634/theoncologist.2014-0060)
15. Guthrie BL, Laws ERJr. Supratentorial low-grade gliomas. *Neurosurg Clin N Am* (1990) 1:37–48. doi: [10.1016/S1042-3680\(18\)30822-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1042-3680(18)30822-2)

16. Hollon T, Nguyen V, Smith BW, Lewis S, Junck L, Orringer DA. Supratentorial hemispheric ependymomas: An analysis of 109 adults for survival and prognostic factors. *J Neurosurg* (2016) 8:1–9. doi: [10.3171/2015.7.JNS151187](https://doi.org/10.3171/2015.7.JNS151187)
17. Incekara F, Olubiyi O, Ozdemir A, Lee T, Rigolo L, Golby A. The value of pre- and intraoperative adjuncts on the extent of resection of hemispheric low-grade gliomas: A retrospective analysis. *J Neurol Surg A Cent Eur Neurosurg* (2016) 77(2):79–87. doi: [10.1055/s-0035-1551830](https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0035-1551830)
18. Claus EB, Walsh KM, Wiencke JK, Molinaro AM, Wiemels JL, Schildkraut JM, et al. Survival and low-grade glioma: The emergence of genetic information. *Neurosurg Focus* (2015) 38(1):E6. doi: [10.3171/2014.10.FOCUS12367](https://doi.org/10.3171/2014.10.FOCUS12367)
19. Reifenberger G, Wirsching HG, Knobbe Thomsen CB, Weller M. Advances in the molecular genetics of gliomas — implications for classification and therapy. *Nat Rev Clin Oncol* (2017) 14:434–52. doi: [10.1038/nrclinonc.2016.204](https://doi.org/10.1038/nrclinonc.2016.204)
20. Xu DS, Awad AW, Mehalechko C, Wilson JR, Ashby LS, Coons SW, et al. An extent of resection threshold for seizure freedom in patients with low-grade gliomas. *J Neurosurg* (2018) 128(4):1084–90. doi: [10.3171/2016.12.JNS161682](https://doi.org/10.3171/2016.12.JNS161682)
21. Jakola AS, Myrnel KS, Kloster R, Torp SH, Lindal S, Unsgård G, et al. Comparison of a strategy favoring early surgical resection versus a strategy favoring watchful waiting in low-grade gliomas. *JAMA* (2012) 308:1881–8. doi: [10.1001/jama.2012.12807](https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2012.12807)
22. Stummer W, Pichlmeier U, Meinel T, Wiestler OD, Zanella F, Reulen H-J. Fluorescence-guided surgery with 5-aminolevulinic acid for resection of malignant glioma: A randomised controlled multicentre phase III trial. *Lancet Oncol* (2006) 7:392–401. doi: [10.1016/S1470-2045\(06\)70665-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1470-2045(06)70665-9)
23. Stummer W, Tonn JC, Mehdorn HM, Nestler U, Franz K, Goetz C, et al. Counterbalancing risks and gains from extended resections in malignant glioma surgery: A supplemental analysis from the randomized 5-aminolevulinic acid glioma resection study. *Clin Article J Neurosurg* (2011) 114:613–23. doi: [10.3171/2010.3.JNS097](https://doi.org/10.3171/2010.3.JNS097)
24. Stummer W, Reulen HJ, Meinel T, Pichlmeier U, Schumacher W, Tonn JC, et al. Extent of resection and survival in glioblastoma multiforme: Identification of and adjustment for bias. *Neurosurgery* (2008) 62 : 564 – 76 . doi: [10.1227/01.neu.0000317304.31579.17](https://doi.org/10.1227/01.neu.0000317304.31579.17)
25. Brown TJ, Brennan MC, Li M, Church EW, Brandmeir NJ, Rakszawski KL, et al. Association of the extent of resection with survival in glioblastoma: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *JAMA Oncol* (2016) 2:1460–9. doi: [10.1001/jamaoncol.2016.1373](https://doi.org/10.1001/jamaoncol.2016.1373)
26. Li YM, Suki D, Hess K, Sawaya R. The influence of maximum safe resection of glioblastoma on survival in 1229 patients: Can we do better than gross-total resection? *J Neurosurg* (2016) 124:977–88. doi: [10.3171/2015.5.JNS142087](https://doi.org/10.3171/2015.5.JNS142087)
27. Sanai N, Polley MY, McDermott MW, Parsa AT, Berger MS. An extent of resection threshold for newly diagnosed glioblastomas. *J Neurosurg* (2011) 115:3–8. doi: [10.3171/2011.2.JNS10998](https://doi.org/10.3171/2011.2.JNS10998)
28. Chaichana KL, Jusue-Torres I, Navarro-Ramirez R, Raza SM, Pascual-Gallego M, Ibrahim A, et al. Establishing percent resection and residual volume thresholds affecting survival and recurrence for patients with newly diagnosed intracranial glioblastoma. *Neuro Oncol* (2014) 16:113–22. doi: [10.1093/neuonc/not137](https://doi.org/10.1093/neuonc/not137)

29. Ramakrishna R, Hebb A, Barber J, Rostomily R, Silbergeld D. Outcomes in reoperated low-grade gliomas. *Neurosurgery* (2015) 77:175–84. doi: [10.1227/NEU.0000000000000753](https://doi.org/10.1227/NEU.0000000000000753)
30. Oppenlander ME, Wolf AB, Snyder LA, Bina R, Wilson JR, Coons SW, et al. An extent of resection threshold for recurrent glioblastoma and its risk for neurological morbidity. *J Neurosurg* (2014) 120:846–53. doi: [10.3171/2013.12.JNS13184](https://doi.org/10.3171/2013.12.JNS13184)
31. Wu JS, et al. Clinical evaluation and follow-up outcome of diffusion tensor imaging-based functional neuronavigation: A prospective, controlled study in patients with gliomas involving pyramidal tracts. *Neurosurgery* (2007) 61:935–48. doi: [10.1227/01.neu.0000303189.80049.ab](https://doi.org/10.1227/01.neu.0000303189.80049.ab)
32. Fountain DM, Bryant A, Barone DG, Waqar M, Hart MG, Bulbeck H, et al. Intraoperative imaging technology to maximise extent of resection for glioma: a network meta-analysis. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev* (2021) 1(1):CD013630. doi: [10.1002/14651858.CD013630.pub2](https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD013630.pub2)
33. Willems PW, Taphoorn MJ, Burger H, Berkelbach van der Sprenkel JW, Tulleken CA. Effectiveness of neuronavigation in resecting solitary intracerebral contrast-enhancing tumors: A randomized controlled trial. *J Neurosurg* (2006) 104 (3):360–8. doi: [10.3171/jns.2006.104.3.360](https://doi.org/10.3171/jns.2006.104.3.360)
34. Pamir MN, Ozduman K, Dinçer A, Yildiz E, Peker S, Ozek MM. First intraoperative, shared-resource, ultrahigh-field 3-Tesla magnetic resonance imaging system and its application in low-grade glioma resection. *J Neurosurg* (2010) 112:57–69. doi: [10.3171/2009.3.JNS081139](https://doi.org/10.3171/2009.3.JNS081139)
35. Matsumae M, Nishiyama J, Kuroda K. Intraoperative MR imaging during glioma resection. *Magn Reson Med Sci* (2022) 21(1):148–67. doi: [10.2463/mrms.rev.2021-0116](https://doi.org/10.2463/mrms.rev.2021-0116)
36. Coenen VA, Krings T, Weidemann J, Hans FJ, Reinacher P, Gilsbach JM, et al. Sequential visualization of brain and fiber tract deformation during intracranial surgery with three-dimensional ultrasound: An approach to evaluate the effect of brain shift. *Neurosurgery* (2005) 56:133–41. doi: [10.1227/01.neu.0000144315.35094.5f](https://doi.org/10.1227/01.neu.0000144315.35094.5f)
37. Shi J, Zhang Y, Yao B, Sun P, Hao Y, Piao H, et al. Application of multiparametric intraoperative ultrasound in glioma surgery. *BioMed Res Int* (2021) 2021:6651726. doi: [10.1155/2021/6651726](https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/6651726)
38. Ishihara R, Katayama Y, Watanabe T, Yoshino A, Fukushima T, Sakatani K. Quantitative spectroscopic analysis of 5-aminolevulinic acid-induced protoporphyrin IX fluorescence intensity in diffusely infiltrating astrocytomas. *Neurol Med Chir* (2007) 47:53–7. doi: [10.2176/nmc.47.53](https://doi.org/10.2176/nmc.47.53)
39. Zhang RR, Schroeder AB, Grudzinski JJ, Rosenthal EL, Warram JM, Pinchuk AN, et al. Beyond the margins: Real-time detection of cancer using targeted fluorophores. *Nat Rev Clin Oncol* (2017) 14:347–64. doi: [10.1038/nrelinonc.2016.212](https://doi.org/10.1038/nrelinonc.2016.212)
40. Kunieda T, Yamao Y, Kikuchi T, Matsumoto R. New approach for exploring cerebral functional connectivity: Review of cortico-cortical evoked potential. *Neurol Med Chir* (2015) 55:374–82. doi: [10.2176/nmc.ra.2014-0388](https://doi.org/10.2176/nmc.ra.2014-0388)
41. Duffau H. Stimulation mapping of white matter tracts to study brain functional connectivity. *Nat Rev Neurol* (2015) 11:255–65. doi: [10.1038/nrneurol.2015.51](https://doi.org/10.1038/nrneurol.2015.51)
42. Contreras López WO, Navarro PA, Crispin S. Intraoperative clinical application of augmented reality in neurosurgery: A systematic review. *Clin Neurol Neurosurg* (2019) 177:6–11. doi: [10.1016/j.clineuro.2018.11.018](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clineuro.2018.11.018)

43. Henderson F, Abdullah KG, Verma R, Brem S. Tractography and the connectome in neurosurgical treatment of gliomas: the premise, the progress, and the potential. *Neurosurg Focus* (2020) 48(2):E6. doi: [10.3171/2019.11.FOCUS19785](https://doi.org/10.3171/2019.11.FOCUS19785)
44. Mickevicius NJ, Carle AB, Bluemel T, Santarriaga S, Schloemer F, Shumate D, et al. Location of brain tumor intersecting white matter tracts predicts patient prognosis. *J Neurooncol* (2015) 125:393–400. doi: [10.1007/s11060-015-1928-5](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11060-015-1928-5)
45. Nimsky C, Bauer M, Carl B. Merits and limits of tractography techniques for the uninitiated. *Adv Tech Stand Neurosurg* (2016) 43:37–60. doi: [10.1007/978-3-319-21359-0_2](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-21359-0_2)
46. McDonald CR, White NS, Farid N, Lai G, Kuperman JM, Bartsch H, et al. Recovery of white matter tracts in regions of peritumoral FLAIR hyperintensity with use of restriction spectrum imaging. *AJNR Am J Neuroradiol* (2013) 34:1157–63. doi: [10.3174/ajnr.A3372](https://doi.org/10.3174/ajnr.A3372)
47. Leroy HA, Delmaire C, Le Rhun E, Drumez E, Lejeune JP, Reyns N. High-field intraoperative MRI and glioma surgery: Results after the first 100 consecutive patients. *Acta Neurochir* (2019) 161:1467–74. doi: [10.1007/s00701-019-03920-6](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00701-019-03920-6)
48. Kuhnt D, Ganslandt O, Schlaffer SM, Buchfelder M, Nimsky C. Quantification of glioma removal by intraoperative highfield magnetic resonance imaging: An update. *Neurosurgery* (2011) 69:852–62. doi: [10.1227/NEU.0b013e318225ea6b](https://doi.org/10.1227/NEU.0b013e318225ea6b)
49. Mohammadi AM, Sullivan TB, Barnett GH, Recinos V, Angelov L, Kamian K, et al. Use of high-field intraoperative magnetic resonance imaging to enhance the extent of resection of enhancing and nonenhancing gliomas. *Neurosurgery* (2014) 74:339. doi: [10.1227/NEU.0000000000000278](https://doi.org/10.1227/NEU.0000000000000278)
50. Reins N, Leroy HA, Delmaire C, Derre B, Le-Rhun E, Lejeune JP. Intraoperative MRI for the management of brain lesions adjacent to eloquent areas. *Neurochirurgie* (2017) 63:181–8. doi: [10.1016/j.neuchi.2016.12.006](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuchi.2016.12.006)
51. Dixon L, Lim A, Grech-Sollars M, Nandi D, Camp S. Intraoperative ultrasound in brain tumor surgery: A review and implementation guide. *Neurosurg Rev* (2022) 45:2503–15. doi: [10.1007/s10143-022-01778-4](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10143-022-01778-4)
52. Gerganov VM, Samii A, Akbarian A, Stieglitz L, Samii M, Fahlbusch R. Reliability of intraoperative high-resolution 2D ultrasound as an alternative to high- field strength MR imaging for tumor resection control: A prospective comparative study. *J Neurosurg* (2009) 111:512–9. doi: [10.3171/2009.2.JNS08535](https://doi.org/10.3171/2009.2.JNS08535)
53. Stummer W, Stocker S, Simon W, Herbert S, Clemens F, Claudia G, et al. Intraoperative detection of malignant gliomas by 5-aminolevulinic acid-induced porphyrin fluorescence. *Neurosurgery* (1998) 42:518–26. doi: [10.1097/00006123-199803000-00017](https://doi.org/10.1097/00006123-199803000-00017)
54. Duffner F, Ritz R, Freudenstein D, Weller M, Dietz K, Wessels J. Specific intensity imaging for glioblastoma and neural cell cultures with 5-aminolevulinic acid- derived protoporphyrin IX. *J Neurooncol* (2005) 71:107–11. doi: [10.1007/s11060-004-9603-2](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11060-004-9603-2)
55. Yamada S, Muragaki Y, Maruyama T, Komori T, Okada Y. Role of neurochemical navigation with 5-aminolevulinic acid during intraoperative MRI- guided resection of intracranial malignant gliomas. *Clin Neurol Neurosurg* (2015) 130:134–9. doi: [10.1016/j.clineuro.2015.01.005](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clineuro.2015.01.005)
56. Coburger J, Engelke J, Scheuerle A, Thal D, Hlavac M, Wirtz CR, et al. Tumor detection with 5-aminolevulinic acid fluorescence and Gd-DTPA–enhanced intraoperative MRI at the border

- of contrast-enhancing lesions: A prospective study based on histopathological assessment. *Neurosurg Focus* (2014) 36:E3. doi: [10.3171/2013.11.FOCUS13463](https://doi.org/10.3171/2013.11.FOCUS13463)
57. Panciani PP, Fontanella M, Garbossa D, Agnoletti A, Ducati A, Lanotte M. 5- aminolevulinic acid and neuronavigation in high-grade glioma surgery: Results of a combined approach. *Neurocirugía*(2012) 23:23–8. doi: [10.1016/j.neucir.2012.04.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neucir.2012.04.003)
58. Roberts DW, Valdés PA, Harris BT, Fontaine KM, Hartov A, Fan X, et al. Coregistered fluorescence-enhanced tumor resection of malignant glioma: Relationships between 5-aminolevulinic acid–induced protoporphyrin IX fluorescence, magnetic resonance imaging enhancement, and neuropathological parameters. *J Neurosurg* (2011) 114:595–603. doi: [10.3171/2010.2.JNS091322](https://doi.org/10.3171/2010.2.JNS091322)
59. Ji SY, Kim JW, Park C-K. Experience profiling of fluorescence-guided surgery I: Gliomas. *Brain Tumor Res Treat* (2019) 7:98–104. doi: [10.14791/btrt.2019.7.e38](https://doi.org/10.14791/btrt.2019.7.e38)
60. Della Puppa A, Ciccarino P, Lombardi G, Rolma G, Cecchin D, Rossetto M. 5- aminolevulinic acid fluorescence in high grade glioma surgery: Surgical outcome, intraoperative findings, and fluorescence patterns. *BioMed Res Int* (2014) 2014:232561. doi: [10.1155/2014/232561](https://doi.org/10.1155/2014/232561)
61. Sanai N, Snyder LA, Honea NJ, Coons SW, Eschbacher JM, Smith KA, et al. Intraoperative confocal microscopy in the visualization of 5-aminolevulinic acid fluorescence in lowgrade gliomas. *J Neurosurg* (2011) 115:740–8. doi: [10.3171/2011.6.JNS11252](https://doi.org/10.3171/2011.6.JNS11252)
62. Herholz K, Thiel A, Wienhard K, Pietrzyk U, von Stockhausen HM, Karbe H, et al. Individual functional anatomy of verb generation. *Neuroimage* (1996) 3:185–94. doi: [10.1006/nimg.1996.0020](https://doi.org/10.1006/nimg.1996.0020)
63. Skirboll SS, Ojemann GA, Berger MS, Lettich E, Winn HR. Functional cortex and subcortical white matter located within gliomas. *Neurosurgery* (1996) 38:678–84. doi: [10.1227/00006123-199604000-00008](https://doi.org/10.1227/00006123-199604000-00008)
64. Duffau H. Brain plasticity: From pathophysiological mechanisms to therapeutic applications. *J Clin Neurosci* (2006) 13:885–97. doi: [10.1016/j.jocn.2005.11.045](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jocn.2005.11.045)
65. De Witt Hamer PC, Robles GS, Zwinderman A, Duffau H, Berger MS. Impact of intraoperative stimulation brain mapping on glioma surgery outcome: A meta-analysis. *J Clin Oncol* (2012) 30:1–7. doi: [10.1200/JCO.2011.38.4818](https://doi.org/10.1200/JCO.2011.38.4818)
66. Mandonnet E, Herbet G, Duffau H. A letter: Introducing new tasks for intraoperative mapping in awake glioma surgery: Clearing the line between patient care and scientific research. *Neurosurgery* (2019) 86:E256–7. doi: [10.1093/neuros/nyz447](https://doi.org/10.1093/neuros/nyz447)
67. Bu L, Lu J, Zhang J, Wu J. Intraoperative cognitive mapping tasks for direct electrical stimulation in clinical and neuroscientific contexts. *Front Hum Neurosci* (2021) 15:612891. doi: [10.3389/fnhum.2021.612891](https://doi.org/10.3389/fnhum.2021.612891)
68. Hervey-Jumper SL, Li J, Lau D, Molinaro AM, Perry DW, Meng L, et al. Awake craniotomy to maximize glioma resection: methods and technical nuances over a 27- year period. *J Neurosurg* (2015) 123:325–39. doi: [10.3171/2014.10.JNS141520](https://doi.org/10.3171/2014.10.JNS141520)
69. Rolston JD, Englot DJ, Benet A, Li J, Cha S, Berger MS. Frontal operculum gliomas: Language outcome following resection. *J Neurosurg* (2015) 122:725–34. doi: [10.3171/2014.11.JNS132172](https://doi.org/10.3171/2014.11.JNS132172)
70. Suarez-Meade P, Marengo-Hillebrand L, Prevatt C, Murguía-Fuentes R, Mohamed A, Alsaeed T, et al. Awake vs. asleep motor mapping for glioma resection: A systematic review

- and meta-analysis. *Acta Neurochir (Wien)* (2020) 162 (7):1709–20. doi: [10.1007/s00701-020-04357-y](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00701-020-04357-y)
71. Cochereau J, Deverdun J, Herbet G, Charroud C, Boyer A, Moritz-Gasser S, et al. Comparison between resting state fMRI networks and responsive cortical stimulations in glioma patients. *Hum Brain Mapp* (2016) 37:3721–32. doi: [10.1002/hbm.23270](https://doi.org/10.1002/hbm.23270)
 72. Romstock J, Fahlbusch R, Ganslandt O, Nimsky C, Strauss C. Localisation of the sensorimotor cortex during surgery for brain tumours: Feasibility and waveform patterns of somatosensory evoked potentials. *J Neurol Neurosurg Psychiatry* (2002) 72:221–9. doi: [10.1136/jnnp.72.2.221](https://doi.org/10.1136/jnnp.72.2.221)
 73. Deng W, Li F, Song Z. Easy-to-use augmented reality neuronavigation using wireless tablet PC. *Stereotact Funct Neurosurg* (2014) 92:17–24. doi: [10.1159/000354816](https://doi.org/10.1159/000354816)
 74. Mahvash M, Tabrizi LB. A novel augmented reality system of image projection for image-guided neurosurgery. *Acta Neurochir* (2013) 155:943–7. doi: [10.1007/s00701-013-1668-2](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00701-013-1668-2)
 75. Acerbi F, Broggi M, Eoli M, Anghileri E, Cavallo C, Boffano C, et al. Is fluorescein-guided technique able to help in resection of high-grade gliomas? *Neurosurg Focus* (2014) 36(2):E5. doi: [10.3171/2013.11.FOCUS13487](https://doi.org/10.3171/2013.11.FOCUS13487)
 76. Duffau H. The dangers of magnetic resonance imaging diffusion tensor tractography in brain surgery. *World Neurosurg* (2014) 81(1):56–8. doi: [10.1016/j.wneu.2013.01.116](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wneu.2013.01.116)
 77. Sanai N, Eschbacher J, Hattendorf G, Coons SW, Preul MC, Smith KA, et al. Intraoperative confocal microscopy for brain tumors: A feasibility analysis in humans. *Neurosurgery* (2011) 68:282–90. doi: [10.1227/NEU.0b013e318212464e](https://doi.org/10.1227/NEU.0b013e318212464e)
 78. Kubben PL, ter Meulen KJ, Schijns OE, ter Laak-Poort MP, van Overbeeke JJ, van Santbrink H. Intraoperative MRI-guided resection of glioblastoma multiforme: A systematic review. *Lancet Oncol* (2011) 12:1062–70. doi: [10.1016/S1470-2045\(11\)70130-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1470-2045(11)70130-9)
 79. Kanamori M, Kikuchi A, Watanabe M, Shibahara I, Saito R, Yamashita Y, et al. Rapid and sensitive intraoperative detection of mutations in the isocitrate dehydrogenase 1 and 2 genes during surgery for glioma. *J Neurosurg* (2014) 120:1288–97. doi: [10.3171/2014.3.JNS131505](https://doi.org/10.3171/2014.3.JNS131505)
 80. Eberlin LS, Norton I, Orringer D, Dunn IF, Liu X, Ide JL, et al. Ambient mass spectrometry for the intraoperative molecular diagnosis of human brain tumors. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA* (2013) 110:1611–6. doi: [10.1073/pnas.1215687110](https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1215687110).